

Editorial

COVID-19 Pandemic: Stress Coping Mechanism and Preventive Measures

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The outbreak of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) maybe stressful for people of all ages and this ongoing COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in many quarantine and social isolation measures designed to keep individuals physically distanced from others for the foreseeable future. Although these initiatives are necessary to prevent the spread of novel coronavirus, they may be causing widespread mental health effects or psychological illness including anxiety, fear, loneliness, social phobia, hopelessness, depression, irritability, worry, anger, frustration, insomnia etc.

The COVID-19 pandemic has effected all the domains of human life/personality including Mental, Physical, Social, occupational, Emotional and psychological as well and the common physical

symptoms which occurs due to this pandemic are unsafe fatigue, frequent colds, nausea, chest pain, eating too much, crying a lot, smoking and drinking more than usual or physically striking out at others by hitting or throwing things and these are the clear indication of stressful life which have evoked due to COVID-19 pandemic.

Who's More Vulnerable to COVID-19

People with all ages can be infected by new coronavirus but people with pre-existing medical conditions, mental health conditions, obesity, asthma, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, substance/drug use disorder, diabetes, hepatitis, HIV patients etc. are more vulnerable to get effected by COVID- 19.

Additionally, people of old age and children, more those people who are helping with the response of COVID-19 like doctors, nurses and other health care providers are all prone to this virus.

Researcher at the University of North Carolina conducted by "Melinda back" her studies show that people because of obesity become overweight due to which their metabolism changes and this shift can affect many cells including immune system and due to this physiological process, these people are more likely to get effected [1].

Other studies have proved that people with asthma may be at higher risk of getting very sick from COVID-19. It can affect their respiratory track (nose, throat, lungs) cause an asthma attack and possible lead pneumonia and acute respiratory disease [2].

Apart from my own experience, people with substances use disorder like opioids and methamphetamine use may also be vulnerable to get effected by this virus as it effects on respiratory and pulmonary health. Additionally, people with substance use disorder are more likely to experience homelessness than other people and these circumstances pose unique challenges regarding transmission of virus that cause COVID-19.

What are the Coping Mechanisms of COVID-19 Stress?

- Take enough care of your mental health by reducing daily level of stress either through meditation, by eating healthy diet or by doing more pleasant work and however if need raised than quickly approach to mental health professionals for further assistance.
- Avoid hearing or listening threatful judgments/suggestions related to COVID-19.
- Develop optimistic attitude about COVID-19 so that only we can look for positive outcomes like all will be well.

- Try to build a good social support of parents, friends, teachers, relatives and talk about it to them and boost your morale.
- Need to develop the sense of hope rather than being helplessness and had a strong belief to our lord or almighty **ALLAH** S.W.T that hopefully everything will be fine.
- Maintain a stable sleep pattern and focus on what you can control.
- Need to accept COVID-19 as challenge not as threat so that only we can reduce this pandemic stress and tension besides, we can also look for positive alternatives by developing counterfactual thinking.
- Take breaks from watching, listening or reading new stories about COVID-19 including on social, print or electronic media.
- Try to do some other pleasant activities which you enjoy a most like playing games, playing with kids, gardening, reading books and magazines, watching movies etc.
- Connect with others on phone or social media like Facebook, WhatsApp or Twitter, whom you had a belief are more concerned about your feeling and expectations.
- Preventive measures needed to be taken against COVID-19.
- There is currently no vaccine to prevent COVID-19. The best way to prevent getting sick is to avoid exposure to virus by sitting at home.
- When you go out in public at times of urgency keep away from others who are sick.
- Avoid crowds and people and wore masks and maintain social distance.
- Avoid sharing personal household items like cups and towels and other belongings.
- Maintain social distance at least 1-meter (3 feet's) distance between you and other people.

- Practice Respiratory Hygiene means people around you are covering their Mouth, Nose with their bent elbow or tissue, when they cough and sneeze, then dispose the used tissue immediately.
- If you have fever, cough and difficulty in breathing seek medical advice.
- Clean your hands frequently by washing with soap and water or hand sanitizers.
- Avoid touching eyes, nose and mouth.

At the end I would like to say “*Every Dark Night Has a Dawn*” hopefully very soon we all will get rid out of this COVID-19.

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